

Role of State in Human Capital Formation in Punjab

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Abstract

Investing in social services is vital for human development and the overall economic growth and progress of a nation. Public investment in health, education, and training improves individuals' efficiency, productivity, and skills, thereby nurturing a capable workforce essential for accelerating economic advancement. This paper examines the trend of public expenditure on health, education, and training in Punjab and its position in India. Furthermore, the impact of public expenditure on health, education, and training on their respective outcomes, including life expectancy at birth, literacy rate, and educational attainment of literate workers in Punjab is analyzed. It is found that Punjab's rise in expenditure in these sectors lags behind both the national average and the progress witnessed in other states across India. Moreover, Punjab allocates the smallest portion of its total expenditure to health and education in comparison to all other states and Union Territories in the country. Investment in both formal and informal training in Punjab has been steadily decreasing, with a complete halt in investment in informal training. Punjab's inadequate investment in the health and education sectors has led to comparatively lower improvements in life expectancy at birth and literacy rates as compared to the national average. Consequently, Punjab's ranking among all states and Union Territories of India in these aspects has deteriorated.

Keywords Public Expenditure on Health, Education, and Training.

Introduction

Investment in social services is essential for human development and the overall progress of a nation. Public investment in health, education, and training improves individuals' efficiency, productivity, and skills, thereby cultivating a capable workforce crucial for accelerating economic advancement. However, due to its large population, India faces budgetary deficits, and spends little in social sectors such as health, education, and skill development.

Increased expenditure on healthcare enhances the productivity of human capital, thus making a positive contribution to economic growth. Various studies (Gupta and Mitra, 2004; Malick, 2015) have confirmed a positive and bidirectional relationship between health and economic growth. Whether a developed or developing country, it is vital for the government to develop high-quality health infrastructure and ensure good health for all citizens. Improvements in health and nutrition lead to a healthier workforce capable of thinking better and working longer and harder. Therefore, healthcare expenditure is an essential investment in the social sector for any nation. The Indian public health system faces challenges like shortage of skilled healthcare professionals, understaffed health centers, and overcrowded hospitals, which adversely affect the quality and accessibility of healthcare services. The Government of India has undertaken various initiatives to enhance health outcomes nationwide. Initiatives such as Ayushman Bharat and the National Health Mission, alongside other government efforts, are directed at enhancing healthcare accessibility and outcomes.

Similarly, the importance of education in the holistic development of individuals has been widely recognized over a long period of time. Several empirical studies conducted by economists such as Schultz (1961), and Barro and Lee (1994), have demonstrated that adequate public spending on education fosters human development and drives economic

growth. Furthermore, empirical research indicates a positive correlation between education expenditure and economic growth (Al-Yousif, 2008; Ojha, 2016). The widespread availability and improvement of quality of education rely on the effective allocation of resources through well-planned public spending. Since the inception of India's first five-year plan, the education sector attracts a significant portion of the government's total social sector expenditure. However, the education sector has been facing a chronic shortage of public funds. Thus, there exists ample opportunity to augment public expenditure to ensure accessible, high-quality education for all children and foster national development.

As India advances towards becoming a knowledge-based economy, skill development plays a crucial role in enhancing human productivity, efficiency, and employability. It fosters a cycle of high productivity, increased employment opportunities, income growth, and economic advancement. However, India's skill development ecosystem predominantly favors formal education over vocational training, presenting a skewed landscape. In 2014, the Indian government established the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) to oversee skill development initiatives independently. Among these initiatives is the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), launched in 2015, which stands as the world's largest vocational training scheme. The National Education Policy 2020 has placed significant emphasis on vocational education and skill development, highlighting its importance in the overall education framework.

Objective of study

The main objective of the paper is to examine the trend of public expenditure on health, education and training incurred at the all India level and in Punjab. The impact of public expenditure on health, education and training on their respective outcomes, namely life expectancy at birth, literacy rate, and educational status of literate workers, respectively has been analyzed. For the purpose, the data from the various secondary sources have been exercised.

Review of Literature

Al-Yousif (2008) utilized time-series data for the period 1977 to 2004, to investigate the relationship between education expenditure, acting as a proxy for human capital, and economic growth in the six GCC economies. The study applied Granger-causality test within an error-correction framework. The empirical findings revealed a bi-directional causality between education and economic growth, contradicting the prevailing notion in much of the existing literature that causality primarily flowed from human capital to economic growth. However, the results were specific to each country and varied depending on the proxies used to measure human capital.

Sharma and Sahni (2015) investigated the relationship between human capital investment (education & health investment) and economic growth (GDP) in India using annual data spanning from 1991-92 to 2012-13. Employing Co integration, Granger Causality analysis, and Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VECM), the study aimed to test hypotheses regarding the presence of causality and co-integration among the variables. The Co integration test confirmed that education investment, health investment, and GDP are co-integrated, indicating a long-run equilibrium relationship among the three variables. This suggests that investment in human capital (i.e., education and health) has a long-run impact on economic growth.

Ojha (2016) employed a Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model to analyze the impact of increased public education expenditure, funded by raising direct tax rates, on economic growth and income distribution in the Indian economy. The study found that a 14 percent increase in real public expenditure on secondary and higher education, funded through a 10 percent increase in income and corporate tax rates, leads to higher economic growth and improved income distribution. The findings suggest that secondary education should be prioritized, without neglecting higher education. Additionally, the study recommends that the government should focus on expanding the human capital base while also encouraging the private sector to boost investment in physical capital to maximize the benefits in terms of economic growth.

Kundu (2018) explored the effectiveness of public spending on the education and health sectors in promoting India's gross domestic product (GDP) from 1996 to 2014. The study used a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model, and the results indicated that public spending on education and health care had no significant effect on GDP. In addition, the findings from the Vector Error Correction (VEC) Model revealed a negative effect of GDP on public spending on health care in the Indian economy. The study also highlighted that India's performance in improving health outcomes is unsatisfactory, with some health indicators, such as infant, child, and maternal mortality rates, being not only low but even worse than in some developing countries. One significant cause of slow progress in these health outcomes may be the low level of spending on medicine, drugs, equipment, and

preventive care. The policy implications of the study suggest that the government should increase funding to encourage the education and health sectors while ensuring that resources are properly managed and utilized for the development of education and health services.

Nurvita, Dwi, et al. (2022) explores the impact of economic growth, education expenditures, and health expenditures on the Human Development Index (HDI) in Jambi Province, utilizing panel data spanning from 2012 to 2019 across 11 districts/cities. Employing quantitative methods, specifically panel data regression models, the analysis reveal that economic growth, education expenditure, and health expenditure exert a significant and positive influence on the HDI. The findings suggest that the allocation of resources by the Jambi provincial government towards education and health initiatives has been effective, thereby fostering enhanced human capital as evidenced by a higher HDI. These insights underscore the importance of structural reforms in education and health sectors to cultivate skilled human resources crucial for economic advancement.

Main Text

Public Expenditure on Health

Increased investment in public health is crucial in providing essential healthcare services, which directly results in improved health outcomes and a decreased burden of diseases within a population. As a result, a healthier populace translates into a more productive workforce, thus enhancing human capital formation. Particularly in developing countries, effective strategies for improving health outcomes often necessitate active involvement from the public sector. This emphasizes the importance of government-led initiatives in delivering healthcare and underscores the importance of public health expenditure in fostering favorable outcomes for both individuals and societies.

Public health expenditure at the all India level amounted to Rs. 26,313.21 crore in 2004-05, which surged to Rs. 139,949 crore in 2014-15. This figure further increased to Rs. 242,219 crore in 2018-19. As far as Punjab is concerned, in 2004-05, the State allocated Rs. 632.24 crore to public health expenditure, which augmented to Rs. 2578 crore in 2014-18, and further increased to Rs. 4082 crore in 2018-19. While the three topper states in terms of public health expenditure viz. Uttar Pradesh (Rs. 19,418 crore), Maharashtra (Rs. 17,934 crore), and Tamil Nadu (Rs. 15,365 crore) have been spending three to four times higher amount.

Regarding public health expenditure as a percentage of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), it signifies the portion of a nation's economic output specifically directed towards healthcare and public health services. At the national level, the allocation stood at a mere 1.1 percent in 2014-15. Four years later i.e. in 2018-19, the share increased to 1.28 percent. However, this proportion remains significantly lower when compared to that of developed nations and its BRICS counterparts. So far as Punjab is concerned, the State allocated only 0.65 percent of its Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) to public health expenditure in 2004-05, which slightly increased to 0.7 percent in 2014-15, and further rose to 0.8 percent in 2018-19. The proportion of public health expenditure relative to GDP in both India and Punjab significantly lags behind the recommended norm of 3 percent of GDP. In addition, Punjab's share has consistently remained below the national average. Thus, Punjab's public health spending is insufficient to adequately address the healthcare needs of its population, accounting for less than 1 percent of the State's GSDP. While various states like Himachal Pradesh and Assam have been spending the highest and the second highest (1.7 percent and 1.6 percent, respectively) shares of their GSDP on health.

Out of Total Health Expenditure, public health expenditure at the all India level comprised only one-fifth, and after a decade, the share augmented to 29 percent. During 2014-15 to 2018-19, there was a notable improvement of 11.6 percentage points, reaching 40.6 percent in 2018-19. Hence, in 2004-05, the private sector accounted for 80 percent of health expenditure, while its share reduced to 60 percent after a decade and a half. Though the share of public health expenditure has doubled over this period, the private sector continues to hold a larger share in healthcare spending, highlighting the deeply entrenched privatization of India's healthcare system. As far as Punjab state is concerned, its proportion of public health expenditure to total health expenditure comprised only 18.17 percent in 2004-05, which declined to 17 percent in 2014-15. However, there was a positive shift in 2018-19, with the share rising to 29.1 percent. Despite this improvement, the State consistently lagged behind the national level performance. This emphasizes the insufficiency of funds allocated by Punjab government to the healthcare sector. Comparatively the three best performer states viz. Uttarakhand (61%), Assam (55.2%), and Himachal Pradesh (51.9%) invested a very high proportion on health.

The absolute figures alone do not offer a comprehensive view of the overall investment in the health sector. So, to obtain a more accurate assessment, the per capita public health spending is analyzed. The per capita public health expenditure is a measure of the average amount of government spending on each individual's healthcare within a given population during a specific year. **Graph no. 1** illustrates per capita public health expenditure in Punjab and at the All India level for the period 2004-05, 2014-15 and 2018-19. At the national level, the per capita public expenditure on health was Rs. 242 in 2004-05. In the span of a decade, this figure surged nearly five times to Rs. 1108 in 2014-15. Then by 2018-19, there was a further increase to Rs. 1815, marking an improvement of Rs. 707. In Punjab, the per capita public health expenditure was Rs. 247 in 2004-05, which increased to Rs. 889 in 2014-15, and further rose to Rs. 1361 in 2018-19, indicating an improvement of Rs. 1114. Despite this progress, Punjab's per capita public health spending, which surpassed the national average in 2004-05, later fell below it. Consequently, Punjab's rank (largest to smallest) dropped from 5th in 2004-05 to 10th in 2014-15, and further down to 14th in 2018-19. This indicates that many other states have made greater strides in enhancing their per capita public expenditure on health. Hence, Punjab's stance on public health spending is notably inadequate, affecting its capacity to promote human capital formation. Himachal Pradesh (Rs. 3604), Kerala (Rs. 2479), and Uttarakhand (Rs. 2093) are the best performer states in terms of per capita public health spending.

Source: Government of India. "National Health Accounts Estimates for India". Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, (2004-05; 2014-15; and 2018-19).

Expenditure on Health as Percent to Aggregate Public Expenditure: To assess the commitment of states towards health sector development, the trends in expenditure levels on medical, public health, and family welfare as a percentage of aggregate expenditure is analyzed. This analysis provides valuable insights into the prioritization of healthcare within state budgets and the extent to which resources are allocated to support health-related initiatives and services. In India, the percentage share of health expenditure to aggregate expenditure stood at 4.4 percent in 2001-02. In the subsequent decade, it decreased slightly by 0.2 percentage points. However, in the year 2019-20, the share increased to 5.1 percent. Thus, in the past two decades, the share of expenditure on health at the national level witnessed only a modest increase of 0.7 percentage points.

Regarding Punjab, it is evident that the share of health expenditure to aggregate expenditure was 3.9 percent in 2001-02, and the state ranked 22nd (largest to smallest). In the subsequent decade, the proportion improved to 4.3 percent, accordingly elevating its rank to 19th. However, in 2019-20, Punjab allocated the lowest proportion (3.3 percent) of its budget to health expenditure among all the States and Union Territories of India. Moreover, the State's allocation has always remained below the national average. It can be asserted that the current level of health spending is significantly lower than the required amount to provide basic health facilities in Punjab, highlighting the need for increased investment. NCT of Delhi allocates the highest proportion on health and demonstrates the highest progress over the time period.

To examine whether public health expenditure has enhanced health outcomes, the impact of public health expenditure in India and Punjab on life expectancy at birth, the most crucial indicator of health, is analyzed.

Life Expectancy at Birth: Life expectancy at birth is defined as the average number of years a newborn is projected to live if mortality rates observed at the time of its birth persist into the future. It is widely used as a health indicator that evaluates both the health status of a society and the effectiveness of its healthcare system. Research shows

that higher GDP per capita and lower rates of infant mortality are correlated with increased life expectancy at birth (Miladinov, 2020). In addition, a significant positive correlation between life expectancy at birth and the rate of economic growth (Bloom and Canning 2000, 2001) is also established. **Graph no. 2** presents Life Expectancy at Birth in Punjab and India. India's life expectancy at birth was estimated at 61.1 years for the period 1993-97, which increased to 64.3 years in 2001-2005, and further rose to 67.9 years in 2010-2014. During the subsequent period of 2014-2018, it saw a further improvement to 69.4 years. Thus, there has been a notable increase of 8.3 years over the time period. Despite these advancements, India still lags behind the global average life expectancy at birth, which was 72.6 years in 2018.

In Punjab, the average life expectancy of a newborn was approximately 68 years during 1993-97. This figure gradually rose to 68.8 years in 2001-05 and further to 71.6 years in 2010-14. In the period 2014-18, the life expectancy at birth in Punjab augmented to 72.7 years, indicating a modest increase of 4.9 years in the State. However, Punjab's ranking in this regard deteriorated from 2nd in 1993-97 to 5th in 2014-18, as states like Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, and NCT Delhi displayed greater improvement. Although life expectancy in both India and Punjab has been increasing, the pace of improvement in Punjab has been comparatively slower in comparison to the national level. Nonetheless, life expectancy at birth in Punjab consistently surpasses the national average. It can be said that inadequate level of healthcare spending has slowed the process of improvement in health outcome. Therefore, there is a clear necessity to enhance public health expenditure to facilitate improvements in life expectancy at birth in Punjab.

Source: Reserve Bank of India. "Handbook of Statistics on Indian States." (2021-22).

Public Expenditure on Education

Many economists have recognized the importance of investing in human capital, a goal achievable through systematic expenditure on education. The public good nature of education requires and advocates state spending or financing for educational advancement within a country. The manner in which the government mobilizes and allocates resources in education significantly impacts the efficiency of the education system. Since India gained Independence in 1947, the government has launched several initiatives to address illiteracy in both rural and urban regions. Initiatives such as the National Literacy Mission (1988), the Mid Day Meal scheme (1995), Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (2001), and Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao (2015) have played a significant role in improving the literacy rate in the country.

Public expenditure on education at the all India level amounted to Rs. 17429.59 crore in 1990-91, which augmented to Rs. 64,236.48 crore in 2001-02. In the following decade, the country's education expenditure rose to Rs. 2,38,678.13 crore, and further increased to Rs. 4,84,923.89 crore in 2017-18. In Punjab State, public spending on education in absolute terms is continuously rising. It was Rs. 538.48 crore in 1990-91, which increased to Rs. 1912.04 crore in 2001-02. In the subsequent decade, education expenditure by the State augmented to Rs. 5640.16 crore, and further rose to Rs. 12,576.79 crore in 2017-18.

Expenditure on Education as Percent to Aggregate Public Expenditure: The trend in education expenditure as a percentage of aggregate public spending provides insights into the commitment of States/Union Territories towards developing the education sector. At the national level, the share of education expenditure to aggregate public expenditure accounted for 16.2 percent in 2001-02, and in the subsequent decade, the share increased marginally by 0.1 percentage points. However, in 2019-20, the proportion fell to 15.2 percent. It is disheartening to witness that over the last two decades, the state support for the education sector has diminished, with the share of investment in education decreasing by one percentage points.

Talking about Punjab, the State allocated 11.7 percent of its aggregate expenditure on education in 2001-02, which augmented to 14.8 percent in 2011-12. Consequently, the State's rank improved by five places from 25th to 20th (largest to smallest) during 2001-02 to 2011-12. However, in 2019-20, similar to the situation with the share of health expenditure to aggregate expenditure, Punjab's position has deteriorated to the extent that the State invests the least (10.4 percent) among all the States and Union Territories of India. In addition, the State's investment in both health and education has been below the national average, with NCT of Delhi displaying the most favorable position in this regard. Thus, Punjab needs to prioritize and increase its investment in education to effectively foster human capital development within the state.

The share of expenditure on both education and training to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has been examined and it reveals a concerning trend. At the national level, it declined from 3.76 percent in 1990-91 to 3.17 percent in 2001-02, and further to 2.96 percent in 2011-12. However, there was a slight improvement in 2017-18 and it rose to 3.87 percent. It is disappointing to note that the share of total expenditure on education and training has declined since 1990-91. Though, there has been a recent improvement, bringing it back to the level observed in 1990-91. Various policies starting from The National Policy on Education, 1968, recommended at least 6 percent of the GDP to be spent on education. But even now, education spending is roughly half of this recommended figure. The National Education Policy, 2020 (NEP) has also reaffirmed this target. In Punjab, the total expenditure on education and training, relative to its GSDP, rose from 2.9 percent in 1990-91 to 3.12 percent in 2001-02 but declined to 1.74 percent in 2011-12. However, there was a slight improvement in 2017-18, with the share increasing to 2.71 percent. Thus, Punjab's share of total expenditure on education and training to GSDP has declined over the period of time and has consistently remained below the national average.

In addition, the proportion of total expenditure on education and training in total State budget has also been explored. At the all India level, the share stood at 24.69 percent in 1990-91, which declined to 20.67 percent in 2001-02. However, there was a slight increase to 22.46 percent in 2011-12. Nevertheless, it subsequently dropped to 21.09 percent in 2017-18. Consequently, the allocation for both education and training in total State budget at the national level has declined over the time period. Considering Punjab's stance, the proportion of expenditure on both education and training in its State budget stood at 22.27 percent in 1990-91, but it declined to 15.44 percent in 2001-02. However, there was a slight improvement to 17.58 percent in 2011-12 and further to 20.40 percent in 2017-18. Disappointingly, Punjab's share of expenditure on education and training in its State budget has not only decreased over time but has always remained below the national average.

In order to examine the influence of public expenditure on education on educational outcomes, key indicators such as Literacy Rate and Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) have been chosen.

Literacy Rate: In India, an individual aged seven and above who can both read and write with comprehension in any language is considered literate. Literacy rate serves as the primary indicator of educational attainment and is a fundamental step towards human capital formation in an economy. A low level of literacy within a population impedes progress along the path of social and economic development. At the time of independence, India had a meager literacy rate of only 12 percent. However, significant progress has been made over the years. In 1961, the rate improved to 28.3 percent, and after two decades, it rose to 43.57 percent. **Graph no.3** demonstrates literacy rate in Punjab and India in 1991, 2001 and 2011. As per Census 1991, India's literacy rate was 52.2 percent, which increased by 12.6 percentage points over the subsequent decade to reach 64.8 percent in 2001. In addition, with an additional improvement of 8.2 percentage points, the literacy rate reached 73 percent in 2011. The progress witnessed during 2001 to 2011 was slower compared to that from 1991 to 2001. Despite these advancements, India's literacy rate still remains below the global average of 84 percent, and the country harbors the largest population of illiterate individuals worldwide.

As far as Punjab is concerned, the State has shown notable progress in enhancing its literacy rates over the years. In 1971, the literacy rate in Punjab stood at 34.12 percent, which increased to 43.37 percent in the subsequent decade. In 1991, Punjab's literacy rate had reached to 58.5 percent, securing the 17th position in the all-India ranking. It maintained this position in the following decade, with a literacy rate of 69.70 percent. In 2011, Punjab's literacy rate augmented to 75.8 percent. However, its rank slipped to the 21st position, indicating that other states have made faster strides in improving their literacy rates. The improvement in the State is also less than the national level. Though, Punjab's literacy rate has consistently exceeded the national average since 1991. Hence,

in order to narrow the literacy rate gap with better-performing states, Punjab must increase public spending on education.

Source: Reserve Bank of India. "Handbook of Statistics on Indian States." (2021-22).

Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER): As per the definition provided by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) represents the total enrollment in a particular level of education within a country, irrespective of age, expressed as a percentage of the eligible official school-age population corresponding to the same level of education in a specific school year. It is a statistical tool employed by the United Nations to measure a nation's education index. A high GER signifies a high degree of participation, irrespective of age, indicating widespread access and involvement in education within the country. **Graph no. 4** illustrates the Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) at various levels of education in Punjab and at the All India level for the year 2019-20. India's GER stands at 102.7 percent at the primary level, but declines to 89.7 percent at upper primary, further dropping to 77.9 percent at secondary, and to 51.4 percent at higher secondary level. The GER in higher education stands at 26.3 percent, slightly below the global average of 29 percent. However, the performance is much weaker than the developed countries like the USA (88.2 percent), Germany (70.3 percent), and the UK (60.0 percent), as well as emerging economies like Brazil (51.3 percent) and China (49.1 percent) (Economic Times Government, 2020). This decline of 76.4 percentage points in GER from primary to higher education, underscores a trend of declining GER with each successive level of education.

Punjab has achieved 100 percent GER at the primary, upper primary and secondary levels of education. At the primary level, GER stands impressively high at 111.2 percent, followed by 106.3 percent at the upper primary level, and 103.1 percent at the secondary level. However, there's a noticeable drop in GER at the higher secondary level, where it diminishes to 71.3 percent. In higher education, Punjab's GER of 29.5 percent surpasses the national average of 26.3 percent. The journey from primary to higher education reflects a substantial decrease of 81.7 percentage points in GER. This trend aligns with the national pattern where GER tends to decrease with each higher level of education. Nevertheless, Punjab maintains higher GER across all levels of education in comparison to the national average. It stands at the 10th position at the primary level, 3rd at both upper primary and secondary levels. However, in higher secondary level, it falls behind five states of India, namely Himachal Pradesh, Kerala, Chandigarh, Tamil Nadu, and Delhi. In higher education, it's disappointing to note that Punjab occupies 15th place amongst States/UTs. Despite efforts to expand higher education institutions in the state, insufficient infrastructure, including human resources and physical facilities, has contributed to the lower GER in higher education. Thus, raising public expenditure on education is essential to increase the Gross Enrollment Rate (GER) in higher education in Punjab. This entails allocating more resources towards improving higher education infrastructure, expanding access to quality education, providing scholarships and financial aid, and enhancing overall educational opportunities to encourage more students to enroll in higher education institutions across the state.

Source: 1. Reserve Bank of India. "Handbook of Statistics on Indian States." (2021-22).

2. Government of India. "All India Survey on Higher Education." Ministry of Education, Department of Higher Education, (2018-19).

Public Expenditure on Training

It's widely acknowledged that academic qualifications alone may not guarantee employment opportunities for young individuals. Studies emphasize the importance of skill development and practical experience in improving workforce quality and reducing unemployment rates. Skill training is a pressing need across India, as it has the potential to uplift a significant portion of the youth population by enhancing their efficiency and productivity, thereby enabling them to secure better livelihoods.

In India, public spending on training amounted to Rs. 642.12 crore in 1990-91, which increased to Rs. 1509.7 crore in the following decade. The expenditure saw a significant surge to Rs. 9177.74 crore in 2011-12, and further to Rs. 10,669.92 crore in 2017-18. Punjab's allocation for training stood at Rs. 22.80 crore in 1990-91, rising to Rs. 50.66 crore in 2001-02, and further to Rs. 170.63 crore in 2011-12. However, it decreased to Rs. 165.50 crore in 2017-18. Public spending on training at the national level as well as in Punjab significantly increased after 2000-01.

Training is categorized into formal training and informal training. Formal training involves a structured and organized learning process within an educational or training institution, usually following a prescribed syllabus or curriculum. In contrast, informal training encompasses learning experiences that occur outside of structured educational or training institutions. Formal training is an essential element of human capital development, as it furnishes individuals with the knowledge, skills, and qualifications necessary to thrive in the workforce and foster social and economic advancement.

At the national level, the proportion of allocation for formal training accounted for 96.4 percent in 1990-91, augmenting to 98.71 percent in the subsequent decade. However, it decreased to 98.41 percent in 2011-12 and further to 98.37 percent in 2017-18. Accordingly, the share of expenditure on informal training was 3.6 percent in 1990-91, diminishing to 1.29 percent in 2001-02, but then rising to 1.59 percent in 2011-12 and 1.63 percent in 2017-18. These figures highlight the major emphasis on formal training, with only a small fraction directed towards informal training. In Punjab too, the proportion of expenditure allocated to formal training has consistently outweighed that allocated to informal training. In 1990-91, Punjab allocated 98.83 percent of its spending to formal training, while only 1.17 percent directed to informal training. In 2017-18, Punjab had completely ceased investment in informal training.

Out of total expenditure on formal training in India, Punjab's share was only 3.64 percent in 1990-91, and has been declining constantly. In 2017-18, the State's share amounted to just 1.57 percent of the total in India. Regarding informal training, Punjab's share was a mere 1.16 percent in 1990-91, and since 2017-18, there has been no investment in informal training. Thus, informal training has never been prioritized by the Punjab government.

To explore the effects of public expenditure on training on the skill development of workers, the educational status of literate workers has been considered.

Educational Status of Literate workers in Punjab: The level of skill and training significantly influences employment opportunities and income levels. However, quantifying skill levels is challenging as both formal training and informal training contribute to skill formation of the workers. Therefore, the educational status of literate workers is considered to assess the quality of the workforce. Moreover, by segregating the level of education, we can evaluate the extent of formally skilled workers in Punjab State. **Graph no. 5** presents the educational attainment of literate workers in Punjab for the period 1991, 2001, and 2011. In 1991, approximately one-fifth of the workforce was literate without any formal education. However, over the following two decades, a significant improvement was observed, with only 3 percent falling into this category, signifying a higher presence of literate workers with some level of education in the job market. In 1991, the largest proportion of literate workers had attained primary-level education, followed by secondary-level, middle-level, graduates and above, higher secondary level, and technical diploma or certificate holders not equivalent to a degree. The smallest proportion was of non-technical diploma or certificate holders not equivalent to a degree. Nevertheless, in the succeeding decade, there was a shift in this pattern as the proportion of workers with a higher secondary level of education increased as compared to those with graduates and above qualifications. It is viewed that literate workers with primary, middle, and non-technical diploma or certificate qualifications not equivalent to a degree have shown a declining trend over time. Conversely, workers with secondary-level, higher secondary level, technical diploma or certificate qualifications not equivalent to a degree, as well as graduates and above, have displayed an increasing trend. This indicates a decline in the share of literate workers without formal education and those with lower levels of education, while the share of workers with secondary and higher levels of education has increased. This suggests an enhancement in the quality of the workforce in Punjab over time.

Source: Government of India. "Census of India." Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, Ministry of Home Affairs, (1991; 2001; and 2011).

Conclusion

The paper concludes that Punjab's investment in health, education, and training is inadequate. The increase in expenditure in these sectors in Punjab is lower than both the national average and the advancements observed in other states of India. Punjab allocates the lowest share of its overall expenditure to health and education in comparison to all other states and Union Territories in the country. The burden of healthcare expenditure primarily falls on the private sector. Allocations for both education and training have not only decreased relative to the State's budget and Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) but have also consistently fallen below the national average. Punjab's investment in both formal and informal training has been on a continuous decline, with a complete cessation in investment in informal training. This further restricts opportunities for skill development and diminishes employment prospects in the state. The impact of insufficient investment in health sector is evident in life expectancy at birth, where Punjab's ranking dropped from 2nd place in 1993-97 to 5th in 2014-18. This decline occurred as states like Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, and NCT Delhi experienced more significant improvements. Moreover, Punjab's progress in this regard has been comparatively slower than the national average. The educational outcomes highlight that in terms of literacy rate, Punjab's ranking deteriorated from 17th to 21st position as other states made greater progress in enhancing their literacy rates. In addition, the rate of improvement in the State is less than the national level. The lesser investment highlights a failure to recognize the

critical role of health, education, and training in fostering human capital formation, which is essential for driving economic growth. Evidently an urgent need for increased investment in these fundamental sectors is recognized. Thus, it is recommended that Punjab should increase the share of public health spending to at least 3 percent of its GSDP, as advised by various committees and commissions. In addition, both the Central and Punjab Government should raise their expenditure on education to a minimum of 6 percent of GDP and GSDP respectively. It is suggested that Punjab should prioritize the training and skill development of their youth and increase their allocation of expenditure on training. This should encompass both formal and informal training programs, aimed at boosting skilled employment opportunities. Punjab could derive substantial benefits by adopting the strategies implemented by the National Capital Territory of Delhi to enhance its human capital formation and fully harness the potential of its human resources. By prioritizing health, education, and skill development, Punjab can establish a solid foundation for sustainable development and prosperity.

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